

EXO-AI: A Multi-Mission LightGBM Model for Exoplanet Classification.

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ABSTRACT

EXO-AI is an Artificial Intelligence model that uses data from three NASA satellite missions, Kepler (KOI), K2, and TESS, harmonized into one unified dataframe to detect exoplanets – planets outside our solar system. While effective, traditional methods for detecting exoplanets, like the transit method and radial velocity techniques, are costly, time-consuming and require manual verification, which can take up to months. Recent advances in Artificial Intelligence have made exoplanet detection faster, but most existing models are trained on data from a single satellite mission, making cross-mission generalization more difficult. EXO-AI addresses this by leveraging a LightGBM model trained on 18 shared features from KOI and K2 data, with TESS data used for external testing despite reduced feature availability. The model achieved strong results on KOI + K2 testing data ($F1 = 0.934$, $PR-AUC = 0.982$) but weaker performance on TESS ($F1 = 0.282$, $PR-AUC = 0.617$). These results show that multi-mission integration improves detection accuracy within shared feature spaces but also emphasize the need for standardized features to achieve consistent, cross-mission reliability. Finally, an interactive [Streamlit web app](#) was developed where users can input astrophysical features and instantly get a prediction score, using the model, indicating the likelihood of a real exoplanet.

1. INTRODUCTION

Detecting and analyzing exoplanets, planets outside our solar system, has become crucial in modern astrophysics, offering critical insights into planetary formation and the potential for life beyond Earth.

Scientists use several techniques to find exoplanets, including radial velocity, direct imaging, microlensing, and transit photometry, but according to NASA, the transit method has been the most successful so far (2023). In the transit method, a satellite measures the brightness of a star over time, and if that light slightly dips at regular intervals, it usually means something passed in front of it, potentially an exoplanet. Missions like Kepler (KOI), K2, and TESS have used this technique to identify thousands of potential exoplanets.

But while detecting these dips is relatively easy, confirming which ones are real exoplanets is not. Each potential detection has to be manually checked by scientists using light curve analysis and other data to rule out false signals from things like eclipses – a slow, expensive process that requires a lot of human effort and paperwork, limiting how many new planets can be confirmed every year.

Recent advances in Artificial Intelligence have shown progress in automating parts of this classification process, offering faster and potentially more consistent validation of candidates (Luz et al., 2024). Yet, most existing models are trained on data from a single mission, which restricts their generalization and reproducibility.

EXO-AI is offered as a machine-learning benchmark trained and tested on data from all three NASA missions: KOI, K2, and TESS. It leverages LightGBM, a robust ensemble algorithm that handles missing values and complex relationships in data efficiently. The three datasets were combined into one unified dataframe, with their labels and features standardized, and object disposition (planet, candidate, or false positive) was used as the target variable. Since KOI and K2 shared many of the input features, the model was trained on their combined data with ten-fold cross-validation, keeping 10% of it unseen for final testing. The TESS dataset, which has fewer features and higher noise, was only used for external testing, to see how well the model could generalize to a completely new mission.

1.1 Contributions

In short, EXO-AI achieves the following contributions in order to provide a new, reproducible approach for exoplanet detection:

- Integrating heterogeneous data from multiple NASA missions (KOI, K2, and TESS)
- Developing a LightGBM model on harmonized astrophysical features
- Focusing on cross-mission generalization
- Committing to open-source development by sharing the model publicly through an interactive web app

2. RELATED LITERATURE

Artificial Intelligence has played a growing role in exoplanet research by helping automate the long, costly process of identifying real planetary signals. Early work by Pearson et al. (2017) used neural networks on simulated Kepler light curves, proving that AI could outperform traditional detection methods. Later, Malik et al. (2022) extracted hundreds of features from Kepler and TESS light curves and trained a LightGBM model, achieving strong accuracy but only within individual missions. Luz et al. (2024) compared several ensemble algorithms using the KOI catalog, showing that tree-based models are effective for tabular data but still mission-specific. Finally, Valizadegan et al. (2021) developed ExoMiner, a deep-learning model that validated over 300 new exoplanets from Kepler and TESS with over 93% recall, though it remains limited to light-curve diagnostics rather than tabular data analysis.

Overall, these studies show the potential of AI in exoplanet discovery but also highlight a key gap: the lack of a unified, cross-mission benchmark. EXO-AI addresses this by combining KOI, K2, and TESS data into one standardized dataset to evaluate how well models generalize across different missions.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Data Pre-processing

Upon inspecting NASA's public datasets from the KOI, K2, and TESS satellite missions, several features were noted as redundant such as planet names, labels, and IDs. Additionally, some columns were human-vetted, like the archive disposition score. Any columns that had no relevance to the detection task or risked human interference were filtered out. After identifying the key columns, the datasets were downloaded for feature selection.

3.2 Feature Selection

For each dataset, only the features describing the signal and the star were kept, such as orbital period, transit depth, duration, radius ratio, stellar temperature, surface gravity, and stellar radius. A mission column was added to indicate whether each entry came from KOI, K2, or TESS, while IDs and name fields were removed. A target variable disposition for every row was added so the model could learn to separate confirmed planets from false positives and candidates.

3.3 Parameter Tuning

Upon graphing each dataset's outputs in Google Colab to understand their distributions and relationships, it was determined that binary classification would be the most effective technique, with 1 representing a "Confirmed Planet" and 0 representing everything else, including False Positives, Candidates, and other unconfirmed detections. While, this way, some objects that would be confirmed as real planets after human vetting but were labeled as candidates in the dataset might be flagged as false positives, this setup ensures that any object the model classifies as a planet is almost certainly a real one, thus offering a stricter approach.

The three datasets – KOI, K2, and TESS – were combined into one unified table with 18 shared features. Feature names and units were standardized across missions, creating a single dataframe for all data. It was noticed that the TESS dataset lacked many input features that are present in KOI and K2 (**Table 1**), which impacted the model training procedure.

Table 1. Features and Their Definitions

Feature	Definition	Feature	Definition
Orbital Period [days]	Time taken by the planet to complete one orbit around its host star	Stellar Effective Temperature [K]	Effective surface temperature of the host star
Transit Duration [hours]	Total duration of the transit, i.e., how long the planet crosses the star	Magnitude (Kepler/TESS band)	Apparent brightness of the host star in the Kepler or TESS band
Transit Depth [ppm]	Fraction of starlight blocked during the transit, showing relative planet size	Number of Transits	Number of transits observed for the planet candidate
Transit S/N	Signal-to-noise ratio of the detected transit event	TCE / Planet Number	Identifier number for the detected planet or Threshold Crossing Event
Impact Parameter (b)	How centrally the planet crosses the star's disk (0 - 1)	Fitted Stellar Density [g cm⁻³]	Density of the host star derived from transit modeling
a/R★ (Semi-major axis / Stellar radius)	Ratio between the orbital semi-major axis and the star's radius	Stellar Surface Gravity log g [cgs]	Logarithm of stellar surface gravity
Planet Radius [R_⊕]	Radius of the planet expressed in Earth radii	Stellar Metallicity [Fe/H] (dex)	Relative metal content of the star compared to the Sun
Planet Equilibrium Temperature [K]	Estimated equilibrium temperature of the planet	Stellar Radius [R_⊙]	Radius of the host star expressed in solar radii
Inclination [deg]	Tilt of the planet's orbit relative to the satellite's line of sight	Stellar Mass [M_⊙]	Mass of the host star expressed in solar masses

Note: Features in blue are not present in the TESS dataset at all

Table 2. Class Distributions of the KOI + K2 Datasets and the TESS Dataset

	Class Label	Description	Count	Proportion
KOI + K2 Datasets	0	Non-Planet (False Positive - Candidate - Refuted)	8,507	0.627
	1	Confirmed Planet	5,061	0.373
TESS Dataset	0	Non-Planet (False Positive - Candidate)	6463	0.836
	1	Confirmed Planet	1267	0.164

3.4 Model Training

The model was trained on the KOI + K2 rows only because they shared similar features (**Table 2**). A 90/10 stratified split was used so the model never saw the 10% holdout until testing. A LightGBM (Light Gradient Boosting Machine) was leveraged for modeling as it is particularly effective for structured datasets like this one, being able to learn non-linear relationships, handle missing values natively, and deal well with class imbalance (since confirmed planets are much rarer than non-planets according to **Table 2**). The model outputs a probability between 0 and 1, representing how likely a given object is to be a real exoplanet.

4. RESULTS

The model was primarily tested on the 10% KOI + K2 holdout that it had never seen before; which served as the main scorecard. Exploratory tests were also formed on the TESS dataset to check whether the model could generalize to a completely different spacecraft. Because TESS does not have many of the features KOI and K2 have (such as SNR), these results were treated as preliminary and were used mainly for generalization and analysis.

Finally, a threshold of 0.6 to classify each object as either a Planet or a Non-Planet was used. If the model's probability output was greater than 0.6, the object was labeled as a Planet; otherwise, it was labeled as a Non-Planet. Results were analyzed using confusion matrices and precision–recall curves to study how well the model balanced precision, recall, and overall accuracy.

Table 3. Performance Metrics Across Different Training and Testing Configurations

Category	KOI + K2 Training, KOI + K2 Testing	KOI Training, KOI + K2 Testing	K2 Training, KOI + K2 Testing	KOI + K2 Training, TESS Testing
f1 Score	0.934	0.647	0.615	0.282
Precision	0.931	0.898	0.996	0.245
Recall	0.937	0.506	0.445	0.331
PR-AUC	0.982	0.812	0.732	0.261
ROC-AUC	0.988	0.852	0.795	0.617

As shown in **Table 3**, the model performed very well on the KOI + K2 training and KOI + K2 test data, with high precision (0.931) and recall (0.937), leading to an F1 score of 0.934. The high PR-AUC (0.982) and ROC-AUC (0.988) show that the model achieved strong discrimination between planets and non-planets with very few false positives flagged as confirmed planets.

To better understand the effect of heterogeneous training, separate models were trained on KOI and K2 individually and were evaluated on the same combined 10 % KOI + K2 hold-out set. The KOI-only model achieved high precision (≈ 0.90) but limited recall (≈ 0.50), while the K2-only model achieved near-complete recall (≈ 0.99) but low precision (≈ 0.44). The combined KOI + K2 training model balances these extremes, achieving both high precision and recall, which indicates that multi-mission exposure helps the model learn mission-invariant representations of planetary signals.

On TESS data, the performance dropped significantly across all metrics. Precision and recall fell to 0.245 and 0.331, and the F1 score dropped to 0.282. The PR-AUC and ROC-AUC were also much lower (0.261 and 0.617), indicating weak separation between true and false signals.

It was concluded that this decrease in performance was mainly due to the missing input features in the TESS dataset. TESS does not include several important parameters, such as SNR and impact parameter, that the model was trained on from KOI and K2. Without these key features, the model lacked the information needed to accurately classify TESS entries. This was considered a limitation of the model, and analysis was continued primarily on the “KOI + K2 Training, KOI + K2 Testing” results (Table 3, Column 1), which provided the most reliable and complete performance evaluation. The persistent drop on TESS confirms that despite the high accuracy achieved by the KOI + K2 training data, further domain adaptation is necessary for full cross-mission generalization.

Results (**Figure 1**) show that 94% of the true planets were predicted correctly, and about 96% of false planets were flagged as "nonplanets". Only 67 of the data points were incorrect predictions out of the more than 1300 testing samples. This confirms that the model was able to accurately distinguish planets from false positives at the chosen threshold of 0.6, maintaining both high precision and recall across the KOI + K2 dataset.

Figure 1. Confusion matrix for KOI + K2 training dataset

This precision-recall curve (**Figure 2**) summarizes the trade-off between purity of detections (precision)

and coverage of true planets (recall). EXO-AI's fixed operating point at $\tau = 0.6$ sits in the high-performance regime: $\approx 93\%$ precision—most flagged objects are genuine. And $\approx 94\%$ recall—most real planets are successfully detected. The overall PR-AUC (area under the curve) = 0.982 indicates consistently strong ranking and a good balance between precision and recall.

Figure 2. Precision–recall curve for the KOI + K2 dataset, showing model performance across classification thresholds

This global importance graph (Figure 3) shows that the top driver for EXO-AI's predictions is SNR. Next are the transit duration and the impact parameter. Size and depth cues, radius (R) and depth (ppm), come next, helping separate true planets from deep eclipses. Overall, it appears that the model prioritizes signal quality and transit geometry, then uses size and stellar checks to cut false positives.

Figure 3. Model-based global feature importance for the top 10

5. DISCUSSION

Ultimately, the findings confirm that while multi-mission training enhances stability within related datasets (KOI + K2), true cross-mission generalization to TESS remains limited by missing features, which is the main limitation of the model. A logical next step would be to incorporate TESS data into the training process to improve cross-mission generalization and test whether performance increases when all missions are included. Another future direction is to experiment with multiple models and compare their outcomes, as done in previous research, or to extend the task beyond binary classification to predict multiple object categories. Or to explore ways to bridge the differences between missions. These steps could make exoplanet detection more consistent and reliable across different missions.

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